

Zirconia Crowns: Aesthetic Masterpiece of the Restorative World

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Abstract

Background : A healthy smile is vital for proper speech, effective chewing, and plays a key role in enhancing a child's self esteem. Traditionally, crowns have been utilized in cases of extensive caries, following endodontic treatment, or to address decalcification and developmental anomalies. In recent years, zirconia crowns have become a popular choice due to their superior aesthetics, bio-compatibility, and durability.

Case Presentation : A 15-year old female patient reported with the chief complaint of difficulty in chewing in her lower left back tooth region since 10 days. Tooth #36 was endodontically treated one month back and it was restored with fabrication of zirconia crown w.r.t 36.

Conclusion: Zirconia crowns offer strong retention and an appearance that appeals to both children and their parents, though they cost more than other crown types typically used in pediatric dentistry.

Categories: Pediatric dentistry, Prosthodontic rehabilitation

Keywords : Children, zirconia crowns, esthetics

Introduction

Esthetic dentistry represents the blend of both the artistic and scientific aspects of dental care. It encompasses all branches of dentistry. Among the most ancient and widespread dental conditions affecting both children and adults is dental caries. Various behavioral, psychological, and social factors significantly influence its development. Recently, zirconia crowns known for their esthetic appeal have emerged as a promising restorative option in pediatric dentistry, offering an alternative to traditional materials and crowns^[1].

Zirconia crowns are a recommended choice for restoring severely damaged teeth, offering excellent esthetic results. These include extensive carious lesions that weaken the tooth structure, large or multiple proximal cavities, tooth reconstruction following pulp therapy, and hypoplastic teeth. Clinically, zirconia crowns are considered effective, with parents generally expressing greater satisfaction compared to other full coverage options. Additionally, zirconia crowns provide excellent biocompatibility, high

strength, minimal wear on opposing primary and permanent teeth, reduced risk of gingival irritation in primary teeth, and enhanced durability. However, they cannot be crimped, so the tooth must be carefully shaped to ensure proper crown adaptation^[2].

Case Presentation

A 15-year old female patient reported to the department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry with the chief complaint of difficulty in chewing in her lower left back tooth region since 10 days [Figure1]. Past dental history underwent root canal treatment w.r.t 36 and past medical history was non-contributory. Radiographic examination revealed endodontically treated tooth w.r.t 36 [Figure 2]. Treatment plan was made after considering the mechanical requirements of posterior restorations for withstanding masticatory forces, as well as the esthetic preferences of the patient, monolithic zirconia

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(here after referred to as zirconia) for the restoration of lower left posterior tooth was advised. In the first appointment, the procedure was explained to the parent and the patient.

In the second appointment, local anesthesia was administered prior to the tooth preparation. Preparation steps for the zirconia crown:

Step 1: Marginal design - The margins received 1 mm shoulder preparation, which allowed more precise preparation of zirconia.

Step 2: Preparation of axial walls the preparation had a 6-8° taper starting from the margin to one-third of the occlusal surface. All angles, margins, and sharp edges was rounded.

Step 3: Occlusal surface reduction -The central groove of the occlusal surface was reduced by 1.5-2 mm. This space allowed for creation of the correct anatomy of the occlusal surface [Figure 3].

Impression making and laboratory steps: After tooth preparation, a putty-wash impression was made from the mandibular arch using polyvinyl siloxane impression material. An alginate impression was also made from the maxillary arch, and bite registration wax was used to record the jaw relations. The impressions were sent to a laboratory. The tooth color was determined under natural light with a shade guide (VITA classical A2). Occlusal view of Zirconia crown w.r.t 36 on cast [Figure 4]. Zirconia crown in left side view w.r.t 36 on cast [Figure 5].

Cementation was carried out using Calibra universal self adhesive resin cement (DentsplySirona). The tooth was rinsed and dried. The cement was applied to the internal crown surface, and the crown was seated on the tooth. After 2-3 seconds, the buccal and lingual margins were light cured, and excess cement was removed. The entire crown was then light cured for 20-30 seconds [Figure 6],occlusion was rechecked after cementation [Figure 7-8]. Radiograph of zirconia crown w.r.t 36 [Figure 9].

The patient was recalled after 3 months for follow-up [Figure 10]. The follow-up appointments comprised of reinforcement of oral hygiene instructions, as well as occlusal examination as necessary.

Figure 1: shows pre- operative photograph w.r.t 36

Figure 2: shows pre- operative radiograph w.r.t 36

Figure 3: shows zirconia crown preparation w.r.t 36

Figure 4: shows occlusal view of zirconia crown w.r.t 36 on cast.

Figure 5: shows photograph of zirconia crown in left side view w.r.t 36 on cast

Figure 6: shows occlusal view of zirconia crown w.r.t 36

Figure 7: shows photograph of occlusal w.r.t 46

Figure 8: shows photograph of occlusal zirconia crown w.r.t 36

Figure 9: shows radiograph of zirconia crown w.r.t 36

Figure 10: shows photograph after 3 months of follow up of zirconia crown w.r.t 36.

Discussion

The clinical application of zirconia, a high strength ceramic material, is widespread. Its mechanical strength is superior to that of porcelain baked materials and lithium disilicate containing ceramics used in conventional full ceramic restorations. Additionally, high translucency zirconia, while slightly reduced in strength compared to conventional zirconia, allows for excellent esthetic restorations. Zirconia crowns are often fabricated using optical impressions taken with intraoral scanners^[3].

Zirconia known as ceramic steel has proven its efficiency in adult dentistry. But to date, a minimal number of studies have been done in using zirconia as a restorative material (partial/ full coronal) for children. Zirconia, which is a polymorph occurs in three different forms namely monoclinic, tetragonal and cubic. The phase transforming property of zirconia facilitates the prevention of crack propagation thus aiding its durability and longevity^[4].

Zirconia materials used in dentistry are anatomically contoured, metal free, completely bio-inert, and highly resistant to decay. The most commonly used form is zirconium dioxide (ZrO), also known commercially as Zirconia. This crystalline solid ranges in color from clear to white and is valued for its exceptional fracture toughness and chemical resistance, particularly in its cubic form. In dental applications, three main types of zirconia are typically utilized: yttria-stabilized tetragonal zirconia polycrystal (Y-TZP), magnesia partially stabilized zirconia, and zirconia toughened alumina. Among these, Y-TZP, a form of tetragonal zirconia polycrystal stabilized with yttrium, is widely used in pediatric dentistry due to its superior mechanical properties and biocompatibility^[1].

Zirconia possesses mechanical properties comparable to those of stainless steel, with a tensile strength ranging from 900 to 1200 MPa and a compressive strength of approximately 2000

MPa. It is a polycrystalline ceramic devoid of glassy phases and exists in three crystalline forms depending on temperature: monoclinic (stable below 1107°C), tetragonal (above 1107°C), and cubic (above 2370°C). Under high stress, pure zirconia tends to crack due to volumetric expansion; however, the addition of small amounts of yttria stabilizes the structure, significantly enhancing its compressive strength, fracture resistance, corrosion resistance, durability, and biocompatibility. Zirconia also has a density of 6.05 g/cm³ and a hardness of 1200 HV, making it a robust and reliable material for various dental applications^[1].

Zirconia restorations are indicated in cases where teeth exhibit significant crown destruction, particularly when more than two walls are compromised, or in instances of crown fractures. They are also recommended for endodontically treated teeth, which are at higher risk of crown fracture and require reliable sealing. Additionally, zirconia is suitable for managing enamel and dentin developmental defects, such as amelogenesis imperfecta, dentinogenesis imperfecta, hypoplasia, and hypomineralization. Furthermore, zirconia restorations are often chosen to meet high aesthetic demands due to their natural appearance and translucency^[1].

Zirconia crowns are not recommended in cases where tooth structure is severely compromised and cannot be restored, or where there is physiological or pathological root resorption affecting more than two-thirds of the root. They are also contraindicated in patients with excessive bruxism, anterior crossbites, or severe dental crowding. Despite these limitations, zirconia crowns offer several advantages, including high strength and durability, the ability to withstand significant wear, and a translucent appearance that closely resembles natural teeth. They require minimal tooth reduction, and their size, shape, and color can be customized. Additionally, they are biocompatible and generally well accepted by patients. However, zirconia crowns have some drawbacks they cannot be crimped like stainless steel crowns, and gingival inflammation or bleeding during placement may interfere with proper cementation. Moreover, they tend to be more expensive than other types of crowns^[1].

Mundhe et al. evaluated the effects of natural enamel, zirconia, and metal ceramic crowns on the wear of the natural enamel of the opposing teeth 1 year after prosthetic restoration. They found that zirconia caused less wear compared to metal ceramic crowns, but more wear compared to natural enamel^[5].

Lohbauer et al.⁶ reported that monolithic zirconia crowns (LAVA Plus) resulted in acceptable wear of the opposing natural enamel or ceramic surfaces after 2 years.⁶ However, some reports also suggest that the wear of the opposing natural enamel due to a well polished monolithic zirconia surface is less than that occurring between enamel surfaces^[7,8].

In the present case report, the zirconia crown was first selected to restore the tooth since the parents required an esthetic restoration for the endodontically treated tooth w.r.t 36.

Conclusions

Posterior monolithic zirconia crowns demonstrate strong clinical performance in the medium term and represent a promising alternative to traditional metal ceramic crowns, particularly in cases where a tooth colored restoration with minimal tooth reduction is desired. Monolithic zirconia crowns are unlikely to negatively impact periodontal health, indicating good compatibility with surrounding tissues. These crowns are generally associated with high levels of patient satisfaction due to their aesthetics and performance. Nonetheless, it is important for clinicians to carefully adjust occlusal contacts, as improper adaptation may lead to changes or wear on the opposing dentition.

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